

MECHANICAL AND CORROSION BEHAVIOUR OF A HYDROXYAPATITE REINFORCED MAGNESIUM ALLOY WE43

H. Dieringa, L. Fuskova, D. Fechner, C. Blawert
GKSS Research Centre, MagIC - Magnesium Innovation Centre
Max-Planck-Str. 1, 21502 Geesthacht, Germany
hajo.dieringa@gkss.de lenka.fuskova@gkss.de
daniel.fechner@gkss.de carsten.blawert@gkss.de

SUMMARY

Magnesium based hydroxyapatite containing composites are a potential biodegradable implant material. Screws made of this material have the ability to release hydroxyapatite during corrosion process which is part of the natural bone composition. Structure, mechanical properties as well as corrosion behaviour of this composite are investigated in this paper.

Keywords: Magnesium, WE43, corrosion, hydroxyapatite, strength.

INTRODUCTION

In the recent years there was an intensive effort on reducing cost in the medical sector. Medical treatment in cases of bone fractures often requires metallic implants which are incorporated immediately after the fracture in order to arrange the fractions correctly. In a second surgery usually this implants are removed weeks or months after the total reconstruction of the skeletal arrangement. A material as implant material, which degrades slowly but reliably within several months would save the second surgery. An important precondition of this material would be that the solute material has to be uncritical for the human being. Magnesium alloys can be a suitable class of this kind of biodegradable implant material [1-3]. While the moderate corrosion properties are sometimes problematically in automotive or aerospace construction, it could be an enormous advantage in the case of biodegradability. Magnesium itself is uncritically or even sound for the organism [4]. Alloying elements have to be chosen adequately for this kind of application. In order to even improve mechanical properties and biocompatibility it could be interesting to reinforce the magnesium alloy with hydroxyapatite particles in order to improve strength and adjust the Youngs Modulus as well as the corrosion properties [1]. Magnesium alloy WE43 (4 wt.-% yttrium, 3 wt.-% rare earths and remainder magnesium) is an alloy which is already in use for biomedical applications; a commercial stent is made of this alloy. After introducing apatite the resulting magnesium based metal matrix composite reinforced with 20 vol.-% hydroxyapatite is the material chosen for this investigation. Microstructural development during the extrusion process and distribution of hydroxyapatite will be

investigated via optical microscopy. Compressive strength and corrosion behaviour will be investigated as well.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials Preparation and Analysis

The hydroxyapatite containing WE43 composite was prepared by mixing a WE43 powder with 20 vol.-% hydroxyapatite powder. Average powder size of the alloy and apatite was approximately 40 μm . Mixture was filled in a AZ31 can and extruded at 400°C to round profiles with a diameter of 15 mm. For comparison unreinforced WE43 extrusions were prepared as well. Materials samples were machined from the extruded rods. For alloy analysis spark spectrometry with a “SPECTROLAB” optical spectroscope was performed.

Metallography

Both materials were cut and the sections were ground with water and ethanol to a grinding size of 2400, polished with a diamond containing lubricant with particles of 3 μm size followed by a lubricant with 1 μm particles. Etching was done with 10% nital for 5 seconds, cleaned in an ultrasonic bath and again etched with a solution of ethanol, water and picric acid. After cleaning in a ultrasonic bath, specimen were dried. Optical microscopy was performed with a microscope “LEICA DMI5000M”.

Corrosion Testing

The corrosion tests were performed on as received extruded pure WE43 and WE43 reinforced with apatite powder specimens, cut perpendicular to the extrusion direction from the extruded bar. Due to the unexpected corrosion behavior an additional electrochemical corrosion experiment was carried out on WE43 specimens in the as cast condition. Prior to corrosion testing the specimens were grinded with silicon carbide paper (2500 grit, deionized water cooling) and cleaned in alcohol.

Electrochemical experiments were performed in aqueous 1% NaCl solution, saturated with atmospheric oxygen. The corrosion cell (333 ml) with a three electrode set-up consisted of an Ag/AgCl reference, a Pt counter electrode and the specimens as the working electrode. The electrolyte temperature was controlled at $22 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. An experiment consisted of a sequence of tests as described below:

- Electrochemical impedance measurements at free corrosion potential were carried out using a Gill AC over the frequency range from 10 kHz to 0.01 Hz. The amplitude of the sinusoidal signals was 10 mV. The first measurement was done immediately after immersion (5 min) and sequential measurements were repeated after 1, 3, 6, 24 and 48 hours. The charge transfer resistance was calculated from the intersections of the circle with the real axis (0° phase shifts) giving the solution resistance and the sum of the solution and the charge transfer resistance (assuming a simple Randles circuit model).
- Finally after another break of 30 min potentiodynamic polarization scans starting from -200 mV relative to the free corrosion potential with a scan rate of 0.2 mV/s

were performed. The tests were terminated when a corrosion current of 0.1 mA was exceeded to minimize the damage on the specimen surface. From the cathodic branch of the polarization curve the corrosion rate was determined using the Tafel slope.

Finally some simple immersion tests with collection of hydrogen and monitoring of the weight changes after immersion in 1% NaCl solution were performed to confirm the observed differences between the two PM materials. The amount of produced hydrogen as well as the weight loss both indicating the Mg corrosion were converted into corrosion rates.

Compression Tests

For the compression tests specimens were turned out of the rods with a diameter of 10 mm and a length of 15 mm. Tests were performed with a mechanical testing machine “ZWICK 050” at room temperature with a deformation rate of $1 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$. For each material five test were done.

RESULTS

Microstructure Investigations

Optical metallography of both materials was performed in and perpendicular to extrusion direction. Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 show microstructure of the WE43 and the composite in both directions respectively. The microstructure of the unreinforced alloy WE43 after extrusion shows very small grains which are elongated in the direction of extrusion (Fig. 1). Grain size is approximately 3-4 μm . The composite material reinforced with 20 vol.-% hydroxyapatite shows also very fine grain size but there are also areas where larger grains visible. In these bands shearing forces during extrusion process were not completely transferred. Hydroxyapatite is not distributed randomly. There are agglomerations which have influenced the development of microstructure during processing. WE43 nominal composition and composition analysed by spark spectrometry is given in Table 1.

b)

Fig. 1: Alloy WE43 in extrusion direction (a) and perpendicular (b)

a)

b)

Fig. 2: Composite in extrusion direction (a) and perpendicular (b)

Table 1: Nominal and analysed composition of WE43

	Y	RE	Zr	Al	Mg
Nominal composition	3.7 - 4.3	2.4 - 4.4	> 0.4	<0.005	Rem.
Analysed composition	5.22	1.8	0.1	0.05	Rem.

Compression Tests

For each material five tests were performed at room temperature and Fig. 3 shows the stress-strain curves. It can be seen that after reaching the compressive yield strength the stress is reduced shortly before the material deforms plastically. This effect is less significant in the case of the composite.

Fig. 3: Stress-strain curves of WE43 and WE43+apatite at room temperature

The reinforcement of 20 vol.-% apatite reduces the 0.2 yield strength as well as the ultimate compressive strength of the material (see Table 2). Whereas often reinforcement strengthens the alloy [5-8] in this case there is the opposite effect. The reason for this is probably the anisotropic distribution of the reinforcement and the low strength of agglomerated apatite itself. The reduction of elongation is expected. Low deviation of strength and elongation is remarkable.

Table 2: Mechanical properties of WE43 and the composite

Material	R _{p0.2} [MPa]	R _m [MPa]	A [%]
WE43	261.5 ± 16.5	420.4 ± 13.7	16.3 ± 1.0
WE43 + Apatite	229.3 ± 6.1	380.1 ± 9.0	11.7 ± 0.5

Corrosion Tests

Surprisingly the pure WE43 revealed the highest corrosion rates in the tests, although it is known that most of the common reinforcements reduce the corrosion resistance of Mg alloys [9]. Furthermore the corrosion behaviour is completely different from what is known of as cast WE43 alloy and a strange shift of the corrosion potential is observed. This is visible in the potentiodynamic polarisation tests (Fig. 4) as well as in the impedance tests (Fig. 5). Although the corrosion performance of the reinforced alloy is slightly better, both show extremely strong and deep localised corrosion attack after 48 hours of immersion in the 1% NaCl solution (Fig. 6). The appearance of the polarisation curves clearly indicate that there is no passivation of the surface and active dissolution starts as soon as the corrosion potential is passed for the two PM alloys, while there is a dense, stable passive film on the as cast alloy. This is confirmed by the EIS spectra as well. While there is a stable, with immersion time growing film forming on the as cast alloy the opposite occurs for the PM materials. This is visible in with time increasing impedance values (indicating an increasing corrosion resistance) for the cast alloy and decreasing values for the PM alloys. A closer look at the corroded surface cleaned from the corrosion products revealed the presence of thin elongated phases (with a tube like appearance) which are more frequently found in the pure WE43 alloy than in the apatite reinforced WE43. This phase (Fig. 7), which obviously formed during the extrusion process could be a possible explanation for the poor corrosion resistance and the deep localised attack. One can assume that they are more noble, as they are not attacked by the corrosion solution, thus causing galvanic corrosion enhancement of the WE matrix. Furthermore the compositions of the PM materials are not as expected (Table 1). There is a much higher Y content, reduced rare earth content and some cross contamination with Al. Especially Al is involved in the formation of those elongated cylindrical phases. How these changes may affect the corrosion resistance has to be checked in further studies. However the poor corrosion resistance was confirmed by the additional immersion tests as well (Fig. 8).

Fig. 4: Comparison of the potentiodynamic polarisation curves of the three materials after about 48 hours of immersion (and EIS testing) in 1% NaCl solution.

a)

b)

c)

Fig. 5: Comparison of the corrosion behaviour of WE43 cast (a), WE43 PM extruded (b) and WE43 + Apatite extruded (c) in 1% NaCl solution (pH 6.5) as a function of immersion time.

**Fig. 6: Corrosion attack after 48 hours of immersion in 1% NaCl solution
a) WE43 and b) WE43 + Apatite**

Fig. 7: Appearance of the new elongated phases in the surface of PM WE43 specimens after electrochemical corrosion testing in 1% NaCl (micrograph taken after cleaning in chromic acid)

Fig. 8: Corrosion rates of WE43 and WE43 + Apatite determined from weight changes and hydrogen evolution of specimens immersed in 1% NaCl solution at room temperature

DISCUSSION

This investigation of a magnesium alloy WE43 reinforced with 20 vol.-% hydroxyapatite has shown the principle use ability of this kind of materials under materials aspects. Microstructural investigations have shown that the grain size of both materials, the composite and the unreinforced alloy is very small. This is a consequence of extrusion process. According to Hall-Petch relationship the small grain size influences the mechanical strength in a positive way. Distribution of hydroxyapatite in the WE43-matrix is only limited. Sometimes particles agglomerate and influence the microstructural development during processing in a negative way. Mechanical strength was investigated in compression tests. Both materials show very high compressive strength. The composite material does not show higher strength and yield strength compared to the unreinforced matrix alloy as it is usually the case. Here the reinforcement does not carry load, which disencumbers the matrix. The reason for this is probably the unisotropic distribution of the reinforcement and the low strength of agglomerated apatite itself.

Corrosion tests have shown that the unreinforced magnesium alloy WE43 exhibits higher corrosion rates compared to the hydroxyapatite reinforced composite. This is unexpected because usually reinforcement deteriorates the corrosion behaviour of magnesium alloys [9]. Passivation of surfaces does not take place. The corrosion attack starts as soon as the corrosion potential has been reached. This however is related to some contamination and change of composition of the PM alloys. Some more detailed studies are required to fully understand the reasons for the observed changes in the PM alloys and how they finally affect the corrosion mechanisms. New elongated cylindrical phases with a high corrosion resistance and/or more noble potential were observed in the PM alloys. Their content is higher in the unreinforced PM alloy, thus might be the reason for the observed dramatic reduction in corrosion resistance compared to as cast alloy as well as for the difference in performance of the two PM alloys. Due to the presence of the apatite particles their formation might be disturbed during extrusion.

CONCLUSIONS

Mechanical properties of a hydroxyapatite reinforced magnesium alloy WE43 are quite high even under the consideration that reinforcement of apatite particles reduces the ultimate compressive strength and the compressive yield strength. As implant material strength has to be significantly higher as the surrounding bone material, which is ensured. The unsatisfying distribution of hydroxyapatite in the magnesium matrix could be one reason for the loss of strength. Corrosion behaviour is still comparable to some less corrosion resistant commercial magnesium alloys, but not all comparable to as cast WE43. However, the apatite reinforcement reduces the loss of corrosion resistance of the PM WE43 alloy. Further investigations for the sources of the changes in the composition of the PM alloys and their effect on the corrosion behaviour are required before studies of in vivo and in vitro degradability can be done in order to clarify the biodegradability in real surrounding.

References

- [1] Witte F. et al.: Biodegradable magnesium-hydroxyapatite metal matrix composites; *Biomat.* 28 (2007) 2163.
- [2] Witte F. et al.: In vivo corrosion of four magnesium alloys and associated bone response; *Biomat.* 26 (2005) 3557.
- [3] Witte F. et al.: In vitro and in vivo corrosion measurement of magnesium alloys; *Biomat.* 27 (2006) 1013.
- [4] Feyerabend F., Witte F., Kammal M., Willumeit R.: Unphysiologically high magnesium concentrations support chondrocyte proliferation and redifferentiation ; *Tissue Eng.* 12 (2006) 3545.
- [5] Schröder J., Kainer K.U., Mordike B.L.: Particle reinforced magnesium alloys; *Proc. of the 3rd European Conf. on Composite Materials ECCM3* (1989) 221-226.
- [6] Schröder J., Mordike B.L., Kainer K.U.: P/M magnesium particle composites; *Advances in Powder Metallurgy* 6 (1991) 281-292.
- [7] Saravanan R.A., Surappa M.K.: Fabrication and characterisation of pure magnesium-30 vol.% SiCp particle composite; *Mat. Sci. Eng. A* 276 (2000) 108-116.
- [8] Ferkel H., Mordike B.L.: Magnesium strengthened by SiC nanoparticles; *Mat. Sci. Eng. A* 298 (2001) 193-199.
- [9] Blawert, C., Morales, E., Dieringa, H., Hort, N., Azeem, M.A., Kumar, S.: Korrosions- und Verschleisseigenschaften von kurzfaserverstärkter Magnesiumlegierung QE22; In: Degischer, H.P. (Ed.): *Verbundwerkstoffe*, 14. Symposium Verbundwerkstoffe und Werkstoffverbunde; Wien (A), 02.-04.07.2003 (2003) 159-164.